

Two-color soliton meta-atoms and molecules: supplemental document

O. Melchert^{a,b}, S. Willms^{a,b}, I. Babushkin^{a,b}, U. Morgner^{a,b}, A. Demircan^{a,b}

^aLeibniz Universität Hannover, Institute of Quantum Optics, Welfengarten 1, Hannover, 30167, Germany

^bLeibniz Universität Hannover, Cluster of Excellence PhoenixD, Welfengarten 1A, Hannover, 30167, Germany

Abstract

In this supplemental document we briefly recap the propagation model considered in the primary document, and we provide a description of the supplemental movies with the aim of supporting the discussion in the primary document.

Keywords: Nonlinear optics, Optical solitons, Two-color soliton molecules, Resonant radiation

Contents

1	Model and method	2
2	Supplemental movies	3
2.1	Visualization MOV01	3
2.2	Visualization MOV02	4
2.3	Visualization MOV03	4
2.4	Visualization MOV04	5
2.5	Visualization MOV05	5
2.6	Visualization MOV06	6
2.7	Visualization MOV07	6
2.8	Visualization MOV08	7
2.9	Visualization MOV09	7

1. Model and method

In this supplemental document we provide a description of the nine supplemental movies MOV01–MOV09, demonstrating various propagation dynamics of a complex-valued field $A \equiv A(z, t)$ along the propagation coordinate z on a periodic temporal domain with extent T , governed by a modified nonlinear Schrödinger equation (mNSE). The corresponding computational problem reads

$$i\partial_z A = \left(\frac{\beta_2}{2} \partial_t^2 - \frac{\beta_4}{24} \partial_t^4 \right) A - \gamma |A|^2 A, \quad z \geq 0, |t| \leq T/2, \quad (1a)$$

$$A(z, -T/2) = A(z, T/2), \quad z \geq 0, \quad (1b)$$

$$A(z, t)|_{z=0} = A_0(t), \quad |t| \leq T/2, \quad (1c)$$

where Eq. (1a) details the mNSE for which we consider a positive-valued group-velocity dispersion coefficient $\beta_2 > 0$ and a negative-valued fourth-order dispersion coefficient $\beta_4 < 0$, Eq. (1b) specifies the boundary condition, and Eq. (1c) is the initial condition. Considering the discrete set of angular frequency detunings $\Omega \in \frac{2\pi}{T}\mathbb{Z}$, the field envelope $A(z, t)$ can be related to the corresponding spectral envelope $A_\Omega(z)$ by the transform-pair

$$A_\Omega(z) \equiv \frac{1}{T} \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} A(z, t) e^{i\Omega t} dt, \quad (2a)$$

$$A(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega} A_\Omega(z) e^{-i\Omega t}. \quad (2b)$$

By means of Parseval's identity for Eqs. (2) [1], the energy in the time and frequency domains can be obtained as

$$E(z) = \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} |A(z, t)|^2 dt = T \sum_{\Omega} |A_\Omega(z)|^2, \quad (3)$$

where $|A(z, t)|^2$ ($W = J/s$) is an instantaneous power, and $|A_\Omega(z)|^2$ (W) is the power spectrum. To assess the time-frequency interrelations within the field $A(z, t)$ at a selected propagation distance z , we sweep over the coordinate t , calculate the local short-time Fourier transform by employing a hyperbolic-secant window function $h(x) = \text{sech}(x/\sigma)$ with width parameter σ , and construct a spectrogram according to [2, 3, 4]

$$P_S(t, \Omega; z) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left| \int_{-T/2}^{T/2} A(z, t') h(t' - t) e^{-i\Omega t'} dt' \right|^2. \quad (4)$$

Subsequently, we use the parameter values $\beta_2 = 1 \text{ fs}^2/\mu\text{m}$, $\beta_4 = -1 \text{ fs}^4/\mu\text{m}$, and $\gamma = 1 \text{ W}^{-1}/\mu\text{m}$. However, let us emphasize that the various propagation dynamics demonstrated by the visualizations MOV01–MOV09 are not limited to the particular choice of parameters. For our pulse propagation simulations in terms of Eq. (1a), we employ the ‘‘Conservation quantity error’’ method (CQE) [5, 6]. Let us note that the mathematical structure of the mNSE (1a), along with the above choice of parameters, yields a very basic setting that supports the stable propagation of the considered pulse compounds [7, 8, 9, 10].

Figure 1: Single frame of supplemental visualization MOV09, showing the propagation dynamics of an oscillating, nonsymmetric soliton molecule [cf. Figs. 5(i,j) and Fig. 6(c) of the primary document]. The different panels of the visualization show: (a) Propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A(0, t)|^2]$ in the time domain, wherein $\tau = t - \tilde{\beta}_1 z$ is a retarded time coordinate. The value of $\tilde{\beta}_1$, used to keep the pulse compound at $\tau \approx 0$, differs among the different visualizations. (b) Propagation dynamics of the spectrum $|A_\Omega(z)|^2 / \max[|A_\Omega(0)|^2]$. Vertical dashed lines indicate zero-dispersion points at $\Omega_{Z1} = -\Omega_{Z2} = -1.414$ rad/fs. (c) Spectrogram obtained at the indicated value of z/z_0 using Eq. (4). Shown is the scaled quantity $P_S(t, \Omega; z) / \max[P_S(t, \Omega; 0)]$. The numerical value of the window-function width parameter σ differs among the different visualizations. (d) Time-domain representation of different parts of the total intensity at the chosen value of z . (e) Spectrum at the chosen value of z . Horizontal lines in (a,b) indicate the propagation distance at which the spectrogram is calculated.

2. Supplemental movies

Subsequently we map the visualizations MOV01–MOV09 to the figures of the primary document and point out the initial conditions Eq. (1c) used for the underlying pulse propagation simulation in terms of the mNSE (1a). Figure 1 shows a still selected from MOV09 and provides a cation that details the different panels of the visualization. Further specifics of MOV09 are pointed out in sect. 2.9 below.

2.1. Visualization MOV01

Full title: MOV01_trapped_state_n0.mp4

Primary document: Figures 2(c-e)

This visualization demonstrates the stationary propagation dynamics of a soliton at detuning $\Omega_1 = -2.828$ rad/fs and a trapped state at the group-velocity matched detuning $\Omega_2 = 2.828$ rad/fs. The trapped state consists of the 1st-order ($n = 0$) fundamental solution of the linear eigenvalue problem given by Eq. (11) of the primary document. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{P_0} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + \sqrt{10^{-7} P_0} \operatorname{sech}^\nu\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_2 t}, \quad (5)$$

with $P_0 = 0.03125$ W, $t_0 = 8$ fs, $\nu = 1.566$. The filtered view of the trapped state, superimposed on the time-domain propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A(0, t)|^2]$ in panel (a) of MOV01 [panels as labeled in

Fig. 1], is given by $|A_f(z, t)|^2 / \max [|A_f(0, t)|^2]$ with

$$A_f(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega \in \Omega_f} A_{\Omega}(z) e^{-i\Omega t}, \quad (6)$$

wherein $\Omega_f = (1.6, 3.2)$ rad/fs specifies a suitable range of frequencies that contains the trapped state but excludes the soliton. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 50.27 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.00637$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 8$ fs. In panel (c), the blue curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapped state, only [see panel (e)]. Similarly, the red curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapping soliton, only [see panel (e)].

2.2. Visualization MOV02

Full title: MOV02_trapped_state_n1.mp4

Primary document: Figures 2(f-h)

This visualization demonstrates the stationary propagation dynamics of a soliton at detuning $\Omega_1 = -2.828$ rad/fs and a trapped state at the group-velocity matched detuning $\Omega_2 = 2.828$ rad/fs. The trapped state consists of the 2nd-order ($n = 1$) fundamental solution of the linear eigenvalue problem given by Eq. (11) of the primary document. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{P_0} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + \sqrt{10^{-7} P_0} \operatorname{sech}^{\nu-1}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) \tanh\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_2 t}, \quad (7)$$

with $P_0 = 0.03125$ W, $t_0 = 8$ fs, $\nu = 1.566$. The filtered view of the trapped state, superimposed on the time-domain propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max [|A(0, t)|^2]$ in panel (a) of MOV02 [panels as labeled in Fig. 1], is given by $|A_f(z, t)|^2 / \max [|A_f(0, t)|^2]$ with

$$A_f(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega \in \Omega_f} A_{\Omega}(z) e^{-i\Omega t}, \quad (8)$$

wherein $\Omega_f = (1.6, 3.2)$ rad/fs specifies a suitable range of frequencies that contains the trapped state but excludes the soliton. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 50.27 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.00637$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 8$ fs. In panel (c), the blue curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapped state, only [see panel (e)]. Similarly, the red curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapping soliton, only [see panel (e)].

2.3. Visualization MOV03

Full title: MOV03_trapped_states_n0_n1.mp4

Primary document: Figures 2(i-k)

This visualization demonstrates the stationary propagation dynamics of a soliton at detuning $\Omega_1 = -2.828$ rad/fs and a trapped state at the group-velocity matched detuning $\Omega_2 = 2.828$ rad/fs. The trapped state consists of a superposition of both fundamental solutions of the linear eigenvalue problem given by Eq. (11) of the primary document. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{P_0} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + \sqrt{10^{-7} P_0} \left[\operatorname{sech}^{\nu}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) + 5 \operatorname{sech}^{\nu-1}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) \tanh\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) \right] e^{-i\Omega_2 t}, \quad (9)$$

with $P_0 = 0.03125$ W, $t_0 = 8$ fs, $\nu = 1.566$, and $\Omega_1 = -\Omega_2 = -2.828$ rad/fs. The filtered view of the trapped state, superimposed on the time-domain propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A(0, t)|^2]$ in panel (a) of MOV03 [panels as labeled in Fig. 1], is given by $|A_f(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A_f(0, t)|^2]$ with

$$A_f(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega \in \Omega_f} A_\Omega(z) e^{-i\Omega t}, \quad (10)$$

wherein $\Omega_f = (1.6, 3.2)$ rad/fs specifies a suitable range of frequencies that contains the trapped state but excludes the soliton. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 50.27 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.00637$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 8$ fs. In panel (c), the blue curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapped state, only [see panel (e)]. Similarly, the red curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapping soliton, only [see panel (e)].

2.4. Visualization MOV04

Full title: MOV04_trapping_to_escape_dw0.05.mp4

Primary document: Figures 3(a,b)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of a soliton and its lowest order trapped state, with the trapped state center frequency shifted by an amount $\Delta\Omega = 0.05$ rad/fs. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{P_0} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + \sqrt{10^{-7} P_0} \operatorname{sech}^\nu\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i(\Omega_2 + \Delta\Omega)t}, \quad (11)$$

with $P_0 = 0.03125$ W, $t_0 = 8$ fs, $\nu = 1.566$, and $\Omega_1 = -\Omega_2 = -2.828$ rad/fs. The filtered view of the trapped state, superimposed on the time-domain propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A(0, t)|^2]$ in panel (a) of MOV04 [panels as labeled in Fig. 1], is given by $|A_f(z, t)|^2 / \max[|A_f(0, t)|^2]$ with

$$A_f(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega \in \Omega_f} A_\Omega(z) e^{-i\Omega t}, \quad (12)$$

wherein $\Omega_f = (1.6, 3.2)$ rad/fs specifies a suitable range of frequencies that contains the trapped state but excludes the soliton. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 50.27 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.00637$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 8$ fs. In panel (c), the blue curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapped state, only [see panel (e)]. Similarly, the red curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapping soliton, only [see panel (e)].

2.5. Visualization MOV05

Full title: MOV05_trapping_to_escape_dw0.25.mp4

Primary document: Figures 3(c,d)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of a soliton and its lowest order trapped state, with the trapped state center frequency shifted by an amount $\Delta\Omega = 0.25$ rad/fs. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{P_0} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + \sqrt{10^{-7} P_0} \operatorname{sech}^\nu\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) e^{-i(\Omega_2 + \Delta\Omega)t}, \quad (13)$$

with $P_0 = 0.03125$ W, $t_0 = 8$ fs, $\nu = 1.566$, and $\Omega_1 = -\Omega_2 = -2.828$ rad/fs. The filtered view of the trapped state, superimposed on the time-domain propagation dynamics of the scaled intensity $|A(z, t)|^2 / \max [|A(0, t)|^2]$ in panel (a) of MOV05 [panels as labeled in Fig. 1], is given by $|A_f(z, t)|^2 / \max [|A_f(0, t)|^2]$ with

$$A_f(z, t) \equiv \sum_{\Omega \in \Omega_f} A_\Omega(z) e^{-i\Omega t}, \quad (14)$$

wherein $\Omega_f = (1.6, 3.2)$ rad/fs specifies a suitable range of frequencies that contains the trapped state but excludes the soliton. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 50.27 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.00637$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 8$ fs. In panel (c), the blue curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapped state, only [see panel (e)]. Similarly, the red curve indicates the time-domain intensity profile associated with a spectral range that encloses the trapping soliton, only [see panel (e)].

2.6. Visualization MOV06

Full title: MOV06_symmetric_soliton_pair.mp4

Primary document: Figures 5(a,b) and Fig. 6(a)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of the two-color soliton pair, defined by Eq. (20) of the primary document. The corresponding initial condition used with Eq. (1a) reads

$$A_0(t) = \sqrt{\frac{8\beta_2}{3\gamma t_0^2}} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) \cos\left(\frac{6\beta_2}{|\beta_4|}t\right), \quad (15)$$

with $\beta_2 = 1$ fs²/ μm , $\beta_4 = -1$ fs⁴/ μm , $\gamma = 1$ W⁻¹/ μm , and $t_0 = 8$ fs. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 32 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.0$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 25$ fs. The gray, short-dashed line in panel (c) of MOV06 shows $[\beta_1(\Omega) + \tilde{\beta}_1]z$, indicating the extremal position of a mode at Ω emitted at $z = 0$. In panel (c), the blue and red curve indicate the time-domain intensity profile associated with one of the two subpulses that make up the two-color soliton pair, respectively [see panel (e)].

2.7. Visualization MOV07

Full title: MOV07_oscillating_symmetric_soliton_molecule.mp4

Primary document: Figures 5(c,d) and Fig. 6(b)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of an oscillating, symmetric two-color soliton molecule, defined by the initial condition

$$A_0(t) = 1.8 \sqrt{\frac{8\beta_2}{3\gamma t_0^2}} \operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{t}{t_0}\right) \cos\left(\frac{6\beta_2}{|\beta_4|}t\right), \quad (16)$$

with $\beta_2 = 1$ fs²/ μm , $\beta_4 = -1$ fs⁴/ μm , $\gamma = 1$ W⁻¹/ μm , and $t_0 = 8$ fs. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 32 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.0$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 25$ fs. The gray, short-dashed line in panel (c) of MOV07 shows $[\beta_1(\Omega) + \tilde{\beta}_1]z$, indicating the extremal position of a mode at Ω emitted at $z = 0$. In panel (c), the blue and red curve indicate the time-domain intensity profile associated with the detuning ranges $\Omega > 0$ and $\Omega < 0$, respectively [see panel (e)].

2.8. Visualization MOV08

Full title: MOV08_nonsymmetric_soliton_molecule.mp4

Primary document: Figures 5(g,h)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of a non-symmetric two-color soliton molecule at the pair of group-velocity matched frequencies $\Omega_1 = -2.674$ rad/fs and $\Omega_2 = 2.134$ rad/fs, defined by the initial condition

$$A_0(t) = U_{0,1} \operatorname{sech}^{\nu_1} \left(\frac{t}{t_1} \right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + U_{0,2} \operatorname{sech}^{\nu_2} \left(\frac{t}{t_2} \right) e^{-i\Omega_2 t}, \quad (17)$$

with parameters $U_{0,1} = 0.050 \sqrt{W}$, $U_{0,2} = 0.141 \sqrt{W}$, $t_1 = 7.207$ fs, $t_2 = 7.271$ fs, $\nu_1 = 0.901$, and $\nu_2 = 1.022$. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 32 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.509$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 25$ fs. The gray, short-dashed line in panel (c) of MOV08 shows $[\beta_1(\Omega) + \tilde{\beta}_1]z$, indicating the extremal position of a mode at Ω emitted at $z = 0$. In panel (c), the blue and red curve indicate the time-domain intensity profile associated with one of the two subpulses that make up the two-color soliton molecule, respectively [see panel (e)].

2.9. Visualization MOV09

Full title: MOV09_oscillating_nonsymmetric_soliton_molecule.mp4

Primary document: Figures 5(i,j) and Fig. 6(c)

This visualization demonstrates the propagation dynamics of a non-symmetric two-color soliton molecule at the pair of group-velocity matched frequencies $\Omega_1 = -2.674$ rad/fs and $\Omega_2 = 2.134$ rad/fs, defined by the initial condition

$$A_0(t) = 1.6 \left[U_{0,1} \operatorname{sech}^{\nu_1} \left(\frac{t}{t_1} \right) e^{-i\Omega_1 t} + U_{0,2} \operatorname{sech}^{\nu_2} \left(\frac{t}{t_2} \right) e^{-i\Omega_2 t} \right], \quad (18)$$

with parameters $U_{0,1} = 0.050 \sqrt{W}$, $U_{0,2} = 0.141 \sqrt{W}$, $t_1 = 7.207$ fs, $t_2 = 7.271$ fs, $\nu_1 = 0.901$, and $\nu_2 = 1.022$. Scaling of the propagation distance z is done using $z_0 = 32 \mu\text{m}$, the time-coordinate τ is obtained using $\tilde{\beta}_1 = 0.509$ fs/ μm , and the spectrogram (4) is calculated for $\sigma = 25$ fs. The gray, short-dashed line in panel (c) of MOV09 shows $[\beta_1(\Omega) + \tilde{\beta}_1]z$, indicating the extremal position of a mode at Ω emitted at $z = 0$. In panel (c), the blue, black and red curves indicate the time-domain intensity profile associated with the detuning ranges $\Omega > 0.1$ rad/fs, -1 rad/fs $< \Omega < 0.1$ rad/fs and $\Omega < -1$ rad/fs, respectively [see panel (e)].

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge support from the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) under Germany's Excellence Strategy within the Cluster of Excellence PhoenixD (Photonics, Optics, and Engineering – Innovation Across Disciplines) (EXC 2122, projectID 390833453).

References

- [1] J. Weideman, B. Herbst, Split-Step Methods for the Solution of the Nonlinear Schrödinger Equation, *SIAM J. Numer. Anal.* 23 (1986) 485.
- [2] O. Melchert, B. Roth, U. Morgner, A. Demircan, OptFROG — Analytic signal spectrograms with optimized time–frequency resolution, *SoftwareX* 10 (2019) 100275.
- [3] L. Cohen, Time-Frequency Distributions – A Review, *Proceedings of the IEEE* 77 (1989) 941–981.
- [4] J. M. Dudley, X. Gu, L. Xu, M. Kimmel, E. Zeek, P. O'Shea, R. Trebino, S. Coen, R. S. Windeler, Cross-correlation frequency resolved optical gating analysis of broadband continuum generation in photonic crystal fiber: simulations and experiments, *Opt. Express* 10 (2002) 1215.
- [5] A. M. Heidt, Efficient Adaptive Step Size Method for the Simulation of Supercontinuum Generation in Optical Fibers, *J. Lightwave Tech.* 27 (18) (2009) 3984.

- [6] O. Melchert, A. Demircan, py-fmas: A python package for ultrashort optical pulse propagation in terms of forward models for the analytic signal, *Computer Physics Communications* 273 (2022) 108257.
- [7] K. K. K. Tam, T. J. Alexander, A. Blanco-Redondo, C. M. de Sterke, Generalized dispersion kerr solitons, *Phys. Rev. A* 101 (2020) 043822.
- [8] O. Melchert, S. Willms, U. Morgner, I. Babushkin, A. Demircan, Crossover from two-frequency pulse compounds to escaping solitons, *Scientific Reports* 11 (2021) 11190.
- [9] O. Melchert, A. Demircan, Incoherent two-color pulse compounds, *Opt. Lett.* 46 (2021) 5603.
- [10] O. Melchert, S. Willms, I. Oreshnikov, A. Yulin, U. Morgner, I. Babushkin, A. Demircan, Resonant kushi-comb-like multi-frequency radiation of oscillating two-color soliton molecules, *New J. Phys.* 25 (2023) 013003.